

CR260-30 was promising against both gall midge and yellow stem borers. Because of excellent grain quality, stable high yields, pest resistance, and tolerance for periodic submergence during flash floods, CR260-30 and other resistant cultures have become widely accepted by the lowland rice farmers of Orissa in recent years. *J*

Field evaluation of rices for resistance to thrips

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Rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) cause serious damage to rice at the seedling stage and to the transplanted crop. Thrips incidence is severe during Jul-Sep at Coimbatore. We evaluated 62 rice accessions received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) for field resistance to thrips during Sep 1985. Each accession was planted in a 3-m-long row at 20 × 15 cm spacing. The susceptible check TN1 was planted after every 10 accessions. The accessions were not replicated. Thirty days after planting, the accessions were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Of the 62 rice accessions screened, 14 had resistance (score of 1) to *Baliothrips biformis*: IET7568, IE-1-7575, IET8659, IET8661, IET9177, Manoharsali, RP2068-18-26, RP2068-18-2-9, RP2068-18-4-2, RP2068-32-2-3, RP2069-3-5-2-2, VRS286-4-1, WGL47969, and WGL47970.

Screening of rice cultivars against rice whorl maggot (RWM)

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In 1984 kharif, 219 rice cultivars were screened against RWM *Hydrellia*

philippina Ferino in the National Screening Nursery Programme at Masodha. At 20 d after transplanting, damage reached a maximum of 51% in KP20. Among the entries. 7 had more

than 40% damage and were considered highly susceptible; 42 scored between 15 and 25% damage and were considered moderately resistant. None had below 15% damage (see table). *J*

Cultivars rated as highly susceptible and moderately resistant to RWM. Faizabad, India, 1984 kharif.

Designation	Cross combination	Leaf damage (%)
<i>Highly susceptible</i>		
RP20	Jaya/ARC5848	51.0
RP21	Jaya/ARC5848	46.5
NDR88-1-1	IR36/T21	42.8
HKRII3	—	42.7
HAUK6-11-1-1-1	IR28/Basmati 370	42.7
TNAU83735	TKM6 mutant	42.3
RP1579-1613-35	RPW6-17/ARC6650	41.3
<i>Moderately resistant</i>		
CR13-3512-8	—	15.7
IR1820-154-3-2-2-3	—	16.7
RNR10208	—	16.7
CR404-20	—	17.1
RP1641-594-2 B	Vikram/Benong III	17.5
RP2199-271-13	TKM6/Phalguna	18.2
RP2091-272-4-5-3	IR32/Phalguna	18.4
MTU534122	—	18.5
NRL 88-95	—	18.9
NDR309	IR36/Saket-1	19.3
OR489-80-22	IR2070-1054/Shakti	19.6
SYE104-9-32	SKL6/Kakeri	21.5
OR448-7-1	ORI58-7-1/IR28	21.4
TNAU83095	TNAU6464/TKM9	21.4
VL27	—	21.7
HKR117	—	21.7
PR25	Jaya/BR34	21.8
BAU149-2	Bala/Blackgora	21.9
KJT2-32-43-20	KJT-2-3243-20/K 35-3//RPW-6-15	21.9
RP1125-629-2-1	RPW 6-13/Ptb 2	22.0
BAU149-27	Bala/Blackgora	22.5
BAU152-64-7	IR2058-436/IR854-65// IR2070-423-2-56	22.6
DSI 15	—	22.6
BAU11-54	Mutant 14/IET5374	22.9
CR406-16	—	22.9
OR371-IP-2	Obs 677/IR2070-423-5	23.1
BS54	Bhawani/IR20	23.2
SYE158-32-36-23	Tuljapur-I/Cauvery	23.2
CRM10-4733-11-422	—	23.2
OR451-3-2	Dasal/OR132-127	23.5
RP2087-14-6-12.4	IET5854/IET6314	23.5
RNR89128	—	23.5
UPR82-83	—	23.5
BAU147-2-2	Mutant gora/N22	23.5
VRS163-2-2-3	—	23.8
IR28224-66-3-2	—	24.2
RNR64118	—	24.2
BAU149-2A	Bala/Blackgora	24.2
OR377-85-6	IR2061628-2-6-4-3/N22	24.4
TNAU83736	TKM6 mutant	24.5
PR27	—	24.6
TNAU83091	TNAU6464/TKM9	24.7

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